

Figure S3: Summary of the *N. benthamiana* transient experiments.

a) Experimental workflow followed to the estimation of the mutagenesis efficiency for a single locus. An agroinfiltration mixture containing the P19 suppressor of silencing, the RGEN and the crRNA/gRNA was infiltrated in three different well established leaves (A, B, C) of three biological replicates (Plant 1-3). Five days post infiltration 6 discs per plant were collected (2 discs from A, 2 from B and 2 from C) to obtain three independent replicates (Sample 1-3). Finally, following the gDNA extraction, the locus of interest was amplified by PCR. The product of the PCR was purified and submitted to a T7E1 assay to quantify the undigested and the digested bands using ImageJ. The final efficiency is calculated as the mean of the three replicates.

b) *EcoRI* digestion of the HDV and polyA crRNAs comparison (up) and T7E1 assay of multiplexing constructs used on Figure 1b and 1c for indel frequency estimation.

c) T7E1 assays used in the Figure 2 quantifications. The locus analyzed is detailed on the right side of the gel and the digested bands are indicated by the red arrow.

d) T7E1 assays used in the Figure 3 quantifications. The locus analyzed is detailed on the right side of the gel and the digested bands are indicated by the red arrow.

